

HnRNP pseudogene transcripts confer cell type-specificity to Xist RNP complex function.

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We recently discovered activation of Xist following inactivation of p53 or Rb1 by loss or mutation of tumor suppressor function and showed that Xist controls a major controlling aspect of transformation, homeobox activation of Pax, Sox, Hox and Hmg families downstream of Dlx and Olig homeoboxes, and that Xist, separately from its role in females in dosage compensation, in somatic cells forms the basis of an epigenetic regulatory complex that functions in gene regulation. The composition of the Xist RNP complex includes the interleukin enhancer factors ILF2 and ILF3 and a KH-domain containing molecule. We describe here that the Xist RNP complex is associated with heterogeneous ribonucleoprotein complex (hnRNP) complex pseudogene transcripts. Xist RNP - hnRNP pseudogene transcript interaction provides an effective means that integrates specificity delivered through a wide range of hnRNP pseudogene transcripts and which additionally alludes to a structural role for the hnRNP pseudogene in Xist RNP function.

Citations

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